

Impact of Corporate Governance and Firm-Specific Factors on the Sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

Over the years, numerous manufacturing firms have been reported to have closed their operations in Nigeria or migrated to neighbouring African countries with a perceived business-friendly climate that better sustains their operations. The dynamic environment in the country has continued to mount pressure on the Corporate governance (CG) of existing firms which is seen to incline corporate strategies towards reconfiguration firm size to sustain their operation in the country. The development raises the question of the relevance of CG and firm-specific factors (FSF) in addressing the sustainability of the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturers (FMCGMs) in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the Resources-Based View Theory. The cross-sectional survey design was employed to obtain data from 432 employees of the selected FMCGMs in Nigeria. Data collected were analysed using Partial least-square-structural equation model to examine the one-way direct hypotheses. Findings show that CG significantly affects sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Nigeria ($Adj R^2 = 0.710$, $p = 0.000$, $Q^2 = 0.391$); FSF significantly affect the sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Nigeria 8 ($Adj. R^2 = 0.428$, $p = 0.000$, $Q^2 = 0.234$). The study recommends FMCGs manufacturers in Nigeria to pay particular attention to performance of Corporate Governance in ensuring harmonious collaboration with their diverse stakeholders, while continuously appraising their firm-specific factors to improve efficiency and firm capability in mitigating the turbulence in the dynamic environment within which they operate in the country.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Firm Size, Firm-specific factors, Manufacturing companies, Sustainability

Introduction

Sustainability is indeed a complex issue, and the complexity varies across jurisdictions. In recent years, due to the emerging uncertainty of the global economy, there is a noticeable shift to resource-efficient goods, with Europe being the nucleus of such sustainable movement. Noticeably, the United States of America provides the leading role in sustainable energy technologies. While China which is known for its harsh environmental state is currently engaging in various research to achieve a relative cut back in carbon emission intensity per person. Due to its limited resources and frequent natural disasters, Japan is also seen to produce a significant number of eminent companies in pursuit of sustainability. Africa on the other hand (except for South Africa), with the majority of its population barely able to afford the necessity of life, is however seen to be many years behind in the pursuit of sustainable development (Frank-Matin & Peattie, 2014).

Hundreds of Nigerian manufacturing companies have been reported to have either folded up over the years or relocated to nearby African countries which are perceived to possess a more business-friendly climate. In line with this, the World Bank Enterprise survey report further provided that 322 private firms closed business in Nigeria between 2009 and 2014 due to the harsh business climate, corruption, and the political environment in the Country (Atoyebi, 2019). Also, between 2015 and 2017, 196 manufacturing companies were noted to have shut down their operations in Nigeria. These companies include Berec Batteries; Exide Batteries; Okin Biscuits; Oshogbo Steel Rolling Mills; Nigeria Sugar Company; Lyle Sugar Company; Matches Manufacturing Company etc. Some existing companies are also reducing their firm size by shutting down some of their factories (Babalobi, n.d.); for instance, GlaxoSmithKline Consumer Nigeria Plc. made known its plans to close its Agbara production facility in the third quarter of 2021 (Olowookere, 2021). Similarly, a year later after investing US\$300 million in its Agbara, Ogun State production plant in 2017, P & G announced plans to shut down the new plant due to high cost of importing raw materials and unfriendly government regulations and policies (Olawoyin, 2018). As stated by Anudu and Faminu (2018), the plant was eventually shut down in July 2018, the company further divested from its Vicks lemon plus plant in Ibadan, Oyo State.

However, given the evidence that existing firms are shrinking their firm size to cope with the turbulence in the external environment, the contributions of certain firm-specific factors would require investigation and understanding, in a bid to ensure the sustainability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria, in the face of diverse dynamic environmental factors. Therefore, this study is undertaken to explore the effect of Corporate Governance and Firm-Specific Factors on the sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The importance and the need for manufacturing companies to operate sustainably cannot be overemphasised, given that an unsustainable company can neither meet its going concern nor compete favourably with its counterparts within and outside its jurisdiction; Neither can such a company enhance economic growth and development through job creation, income generation for the government, and offering sustainable product to the citizens. Various studies have been conducted on the sustainability of Nigerian manufacturing firms. For instance, financial decisions and sustainability of cash flow in Nigerian manufacturing companies have been studied (Imhanzenube & Adeyemi, 2020). Assessment of the effective Factors of Social Responsibility Disclosure of Listed Consumer Goods Firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange has also been researched (Onyali, Okerekeoti & Uchegbu, 2020). The interaction between firm characteristics and sustainability reporting of Listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria has been investigated (Tihamiyu, Oyedokun & Ademola, 2021). The implication of corporate social cost on the profitability of oil marketing companies in Nigeria has been investigated (Kaoje, Sani, Tank, Babangida & Sabo, 2020). However, the interaction between corporate governance with particular emphasis on accountability, leadership, and stakeholder management, as well as firm-specific factors such as firm size and operational efficiency, and sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCGs) manufacturing companies in Nigeria require scholarly attention. This gap in existing literature suggests that nothing concrete is known within empiricism of how corporate governance and firm-specific factors interact to address sustainability concerns for FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study therefore sought to investigate Corporate Governance, firm-specific factors, and the Sustainability of FMCGs Companies in Nigeria, and raised the question of what relevance are these dimensions to the sustainability of FMCGs Companies in Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

1. examine the effect of corporate governance on the sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.
2. assess how firm-specific factors affect the sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

Sustainability

In general terms, sustainability refers to the ability to maintain a certain rate or level of an activity, object, or subject over time. It is defined as the ability to continuously meet or achieve current needs or goals without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet theirs (UN, 2021). This definition follows the concept of sustainable development as

proposed by the world commission on environment and development, which is an initiative of the United Nations introduced in 1987. In line with this, Bansal and Agarwal (2021) stated that firms are required to pursue their wealth creation agenda while contributing to the reduction of poverty without impairing the natural environment.

According to Farinloye (2018) sustainability depicts the ability to continue an endeavour indefinitely through resource regeneration at a rate equal to or better still higher than the rate at which such resources are consumed, in such a manner that the integrity of natural biotic systems is not impaired. Sustainability, therefore, portrays conducting a current action to meet a present need while giving due consideration to the impact that action may have on future generations' ability to meet their own needs (UN). Sustainability or sustainable development as initially proposed in 1979 by Rene Passet is built on three pillars viz the economy, the society, and the environment. These pillars are also respectively referred to as the economic pillar, social pillar, and environmental pillar. A fourth pillar, the cultural pillar is also included by some authors (Farinloye, 2018).

Corporate sustainability is a unified concept of both top-down and bottom-up approaches. It views a firm responsibility to be beyond profit-making. Strong corporate sustainability recognizes the rights and social needs of the people. Two social activities define corporate sustainability, viz: (i) global environmental activity with emphasis on sustaining the global environment and sustainable development; and (ii) business activity with a focus on a specialized area of a broader market that the firm can serve to differentiate itself while factoring in societal concerns (corporate environmentalism). Corporate Sustainability, therefore, could be said to be a stakeholder's right recognition concept (Sheehy & Farneti, 2021). Thus, Corporate Sustainability can be further defined as a business approach that maximizes stockholder's wealth, while contributing to societal development in a manner that the firm's activity does not destroy environmental assets.

The above definition captures the primary ingredients of sustainability (Economic, Social, and Environment) as initially proposed in 1979 by Rene Passet. Furthermore, as a topmost priority of the international community, and the main agenda of the post-2015 development agenda; the United Nations (UN) systems currently dwell on all these three pillars. The Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) operates at the centre of this system as the platform that unites, follow-up, and review all effort on sustainable development. The United Nations (UN) 2030 Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs), with 195 nations around the world in agreement proposes 17 SDGs targeted to be achieved by the year 2030. These goals include eradication of poverty; Zero hunger; Good health and well-being; Quality Education; Gender Equality; Clean water Sanitation; Decent work, and Economic

Growth etc. To accomplish these goals the UN intends to engage governments, businesses, media, and others (United Nation).

Corporate Governance

According to Oyedokun (2019), corporate governance refers to the way organizations are directed and controlled, in alignment with the interest of various stakeholders. Corporate Governance offers a context within which firm conduct their activities harmoniously through the identification and distribution of rights and responsibilities of diverse stakeholders (Zinkni, 2019). It factors the rights and obligations of diverse stakeholders and provides the rules governing how they relate to one another and provides assurance to investors on the efficiency of the firm leadership in running the affairs of the firm (Setyahdi & Narsa, 2020). Corporate Governance is based on the principles of accountability, transparency, responsibility, and fairness (Chen, n.d.). It specifies those given power, charged with accountability, and decision-making responsibilities in an organization, and further relates to the mannerism by which firms are governed and the objective it intends to achieve (Chartered Governance Institute UK & Ireland); while stipulating how responsibilities and rights are distributed amongst various stakeholders which include its stockholders, board of directors, managers (Castrillon & Alfonso, 2021), employees, creditors, customers, and the community (Oyedokun, 2019). The board of directors is pivotal to corporate governance, given that they have the power to take such vital decisions that could affect all the other stakeholders (Alanzi, 2019). Likewise, E-Vahdati, Zulkifli and Zakariya (2018) stated the inclination of the organization toward sustainable practices depends on the seriousness of its corporate governance.

The pioneering Code of Best Practice on Corporate Governance in Nigeria was issued under the Security and Exchange Commission Code 2003; Although, several laws contribute to the practice of corporate governance as it exists in Nigeria. The major regulation is however provided under the Companies and Allied Matters Act Cap c20. These laws aim to ensure that firms in the country are managed in a way that promotes accountability, responsibility, and due consideration to relevant stakeholders (Jegade, Arb & Idiaru, n.d.). The theoretical frame of corporate governance concern is also referred to as the “4 p's” of corporate governance. The 4 p's stand for people (hiring the right people for the job); performance (hiring competent hands with required skills); Process and policies (formulating and installing the right policy and process that enhances monitoring and feedback) (Agbakoba, n.d.).

Firm-Specific Factors

Firm-specific factors can be described as those resources/capabilities of a firm that are seen to be of relevance in deciding the course of action. This study considers those internal factors that have been seen to be of focus by firms in Nigeria in their effort to remain operational in the face of the diverse external forces impacting their sustainability. Therefore, the firm-specific factors considered in this study are the firm size and level of efficiency of the firm.

The size of a firm can be defined by the firm's total assets, total revenue, market value of equity, number of employees etc. The use of revenue to measure firm size is a backwards-looking approach though indicates the firm's market competition. The total assets approach indicates resources utilized by the firm to meet its objective. The market value of equity approach provides an indication of the firm's equity market condition as well as its growth prospects (Dang, Li & Yang, 2018).

Firm size serves as a tool used by firms to gain a competitive advantage over their counterparts in an industry. Larger firms have been observed to have better financial performance and pay better wages to their employees (Umukoro, Uwuigbe, Obigbemi, Babajide, Eluyela & Ofe, 2021), and further serve as a common determinant of the disclosure requirement of companies. Bigger companies are often required to disclose more information in their financial reports, which is also associated with the political pressure on CSR performance (Nasution, Erlina & Tamizi, 2018).

Firm size has been identified as a significant factor in the determination of a firm's profitability (Gaio & Henriques, 2018). Larger firms are more prone to potential losses due to the quantum of assets employed in their operations. Also, Eyer (2018) posited that large firms tend to be more cautious in their dealings especially if the assets and liabilities increase alongside the size of the firm.

An Industry is typically made up of firms, and these firms come in different sizes with varying production costs. The ideal firm size from the angle of the economist is that size that promotes efficiency (i.e., the lowest production cost per unit). Also, the firm is made up of plants or factories, etc. where goods and services are produced and supplied. The plant contains both pieces of machinery, equipment, workers, land, etc., and the firm may own one or various plants either geared towards producing goods/services or multiple goods/services. Thus, a firm is an entity that owns, controls, and manages a plant alongside other productive resources with the view of making a profit. Hence, the quantum of plants

and productive resources owned, managed, and controlled by the firm determines the size of the firm. A firm is said to be at optimum (optimum firm) when after considering all existing conditions (both internal capacity and external dynamism) has the lowest average cost per unit produced in the long run. The optimum firm size, therefore, is the size of the firm which best supports its optimum position, any further increase in the firm size beyond such point produces a diminishing return (Sindhuja, n.d.).

Efficiency connotes the highest level of performance attainable using available resources to achieve a maximum level of output. It is characterized by doing away with those resources that are not required by the firm to achieve its outputs, thereby cutting the cost associated with meeting set goals (Banton, 2022). Companies employ different strategies to improve their efficiency. For instance, Internal efficiency and effective use of machinery could be attained by structuring operational strategies in line with the competitive strategy of the firm. Also, lean manufacturing practices are another tool used by manufacturing firms to curb wastage and improve efficiency (Sahoo, 2020). Furthermore, with the advent of globalization, manufacturing firms also capitalize on the jurisdictional difference in the cost of labour and raw materials supplies to improve their efficiency. The concept of industry 4.0 is also another efficiency tool used by manufacturing companies in recent years. This is also referred to as the fourth industrial revolution and it seeks to proffer efficient solutions through the lens of technological advancements such as industrial smart devices and applications to enhance production processes, customer relationships, and competitiveness in the manufacturing sector. This system ensures that production meets the required quality, quantity, and timely delivery system is achieved to the right customer and at the right location, in an environmentally friendly manner (Salam, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the resources-based view theory which was introduced by Barney (1991). The theory provides that an organization is made up of various resources which are both tangible and intangible (such as Knowledge, skills, experience, technology, information, and data), the combination of these resources gives birth to other specialised resources (Capabilities) which either individually or collectively create strategic capabilities that provide a sustainable competitive advantage to the organization (Kor, Mahoney, Siemsen & Tan, 2016). The key proposition of RBV is that firms can attain sustainable competitive advantage when the resources and capabilities applied by the firm are valuable (V), rare (R), Costly to imitate (I), and non-substitutable (N), furthermore, when there is an appropriate organization in place to capture value imbedded in those resources (O)- VRIN/O (Jurevicious, n.d.). The thought around the concept of RBV as a way

of attaining sustained competitive advantage surfaced in the 1980s and 1990s as a result of the publication of proponents of the theory such as Birger Wernfelt, Jay Baney, C.K. Prahalad and Gary Hemel. RBV rests on two important assumptions, the assumption of heterogeneity and immobility. The heterogeneous assumption holds that firms possess different resources, skills, capabilities etc., which enables them to adopt different strategies to outdo each other; while the assumption of Immobility depicts those resources cannot in the short run be moved from one firm to the other, thus the resources and strategies of one firm cannot be copied by a rival firm. The resource-based view aids organizations to achieve an efficient allocation of resources, cross-functional use of resources, and a competitive advantage that can be preserved (Sridharan, n.d.).

Like most theories, the RBV has its critics. The line of argument of these critics could be categorized into eight broad groups (Kraaijenbrink, Spender & Groen, 2010). The first group includes Thomas C. Powell, Tom Connor, Tony McGuniees, and Robert E. Morgan. This group argues that the RBV theory lacks substantive managerial implication (Powell, 2001), and appears to advocate for firms to obtain resources that satisfy the VRIN (valuable (V), rare (R), Costly to imitate (I), and non-substitutable (N)) provision but fails to advise on how this could be achieved (Connor, 2002). Furthermore, it trivializes the property-rights issues and exaggerates the ability of managers to forecast events and exercise control over resources (McGuinness & Morgan, 2020). Proponents of the theory however debunked this line of criticism and explained that the RBV is, but a theory aimed at explaining sustainable competitive advantage achieved by some firms over others (Nelson, 1991), thus it is not meant to offer prescriptions to management (Barney, 2005).

The second group of critics like David J. Collis also argued that the RBV would mean a situation of infinite regress, given that a firm that is seen to be at a competitive advantage today, could be surpassed sooner or later by another firm that has the superior capability to develop better innovative products. According to Collis (1994), counter this point of criticism, some scholars argued that management or economics is not a movement for positive certainty, it is an open-ended practical approach, thus this line of criticism cannot hold (Kraaijenbrink, Spender & Groen, 2010). We find Michael Gilbert in the third group of critics. The group argues that the application of the Resource-Based view theory is overly limited and further point out that the understanding of the unique nature of resources, meddles with heterogeneity and immobility thus rubs the theory of capacity to generalise (Gibbert, 2006). Also, Levitas (2006), this line of argument has however been described as too academic to be applicable.

The fourth group of critics argues that sustainable competitive advantage cannot be achieved, given that RBV requires a continuous rejig of the firm's resources; with the implication that advantages created as a result would only be temporal and ever-changing (Fiol, 2001). To correct the perception behind this line of criticism, Barney, Wright and Ketchen (2001) argued that the logic behind the RBV applies to the resources of the firm just as much as it does to the firm's dynamic capabilities. The fifth group criticizes the RBV to have failed in its attempt as a theory of the firm. This group of critics includes Kathleen Conner (Conner, 1991), Bruce Kogut and Udo Zander (Kogut & Zander, 1992). Their main point of argument was that the effort of the RBV to be a theory of the firm is materially different from other theories of Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) (Williamson & Winter, 1993). To this, proponents of the RBV argue that the RBV does not intend to explain the boundaries of firms, given that TCE already explains such boundaries, thus there is no reason to require the RBV to meet such criteria (Kraaijenbrink, Spender & Groen, 2010).

The sixth group of critics argues about the necessity and sufficiency of the theory. Among these critics are Craig Armstrong and Katsuhiko Shimizu, who supports that the RBV lacks empirical support (Armstrong & Shimizu, 2007). The seventh group of critics argues that the RBV is overly imprecise and tautological to qualify for a true theory (Locket, Thomson & Morgenstern, 2009). Moreover, the eighth criticism forward that the definition of resources is not practical, given that the concept of resources is too inclusive and suggests that there is no limit to what the firm could categorise as a resource and how such resource could be categorised into basic resources and capabilities required to efficiently use the resources, as well as how the various resources of the firm can contribute to sustainable competitive advantage. Thus, there is a need for RBV to reconsider these three fundamental issues to enable it to gain the position of a central theory of sustainable competitive advantage (Kraaijenbrink, Spender & Groen, 2010).

Finally, this study gives further support to the RBV given that the capacity of a firm to perform sustainably is dependent on the resources it acquires and the characteristics of these resources (which in this case has VIRN/O features). Thus, RBV provides the theoretical explanations for the functional association between the second group of the independent variable (firm-specific factors) and the dependent variable (Sustainability performance) investigated in this study. \

Empirical Review

Several dimensions of corporate governance and their influence on sustainable development have been investigated in different parts of the world. In a systematic literature review carried out to investigate the integration of corporate governance with

sustainability, the findings were that the interaction between corporate governance and sustainability is interpreted differently in different jurisdictions. Notably, the study also established that leadership, vision, and mission are the most significant drivers of sustainability framework in corporate governance. Also, the sustainability framework provides diverse options that aid in improving organizational efficiency (E-Vahdati, Zulkifi & Zakariya, 2018). In a later study, Utami, Cahyana, Nimran & Iqbal (2020) also found that Corporate Governance alongside increased strategic leadership, corporate culture, business infrastructure, and corporate alignment through corporate hospitality ensures a greater level of Corporate Sustainability. Maali, Rakia and Khaireddine (2021) arrived at a similar conclusion with the findings that Corporate Governance exerts a positive effect on sustainability performance. These results are also corroborated by Antwi-Adjei, Kong, Kwame and Antwi-Adjei (2020), and LazaroIU, Ionesu, Andronie and Dijmarescy (2020) which established that Corporate Governance exerts a positive effect on sustainability performance.

Firm size and its influence on corporate performance have also been investigated by some scholars. For instance, in Nigeria, a study was conducted to establish the controlling effect of company size and age of selected listed companies on the interaction between corporate governance and sustainability reporting. The study adopted the ex-post facto research design and sampled 42 listed companies out of a total population of 169 companies listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange as of December 31, 2019. Data extracted from the listed companies annual accounts cover a period of 10 years from 2010 to 2019. The collected data were analysed using descriptive and multiple regression analysis. The study result shows that firm size, and age has control over how corporate governance impact sustainability reporting in Nigeria. The study also found that board size, board independence, female director, board ownership, firm size, and company age have a significant relationship with sustainability reporting in Nigeria. CEO of companies serving as chairman of the board of directors (CEO duality) was however discovered to have no significant influence over sustainability reporting (Ajao & Moses, 2021). Some studies have also been conducted on the interaction between the selected individual proxies of firm-specific factors and individual dimensions of sustainable development. In this regard, the effect of firm size on the social dimension of sustainability has been studied. For instance, in an effort to gather empirical evidence on the impact of profitability, firm size, and foreign ownership on CSR disclosure, a study conducted in Indonesia by analysing data obtained from a sample of 84 Indonesian firms (2016-2018) using Regression and Classic assumption Test found that firm size, as well as profitability, have a significant effect on CSR disclosure. (Kardiyanti & Dwiranda, 2020).

Away from reporting to performance, a study conducted in Indonesia to research the effect of Firm size, Board gender diversity, and Industry type on CSR using data for the period 2017-2018 obtained from listed Indonesian firms found that firm size does not have a significant impact on CSR performance. Unlike this study, the findings of another research conducted in Indonesia to find empirical evidence of the impact of firm size, leverage, growth, and liquidity on firm performance established that firm size exerts a significant and positive influence on firm performance. This result was arrived at through an analysis of the secondary data collected on 44 sampled listed Indonesian manufacturing firms for the period 2017-2019 using EViews 11 (Ekadjaja, Wijaya & Vernetta, 2021). Likewise, the result of another study conducted in Nigeria to investigate the interaction between firm-specific factors and sustainability of listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria found that firm size exerts a positive and significant effect on CSR performance. The study employed the ex-post facto research design and used data obtained from 60% of listed CGMCs listed on the Nigeria Stock exchange as of March 2021. Collected data for the study were analysed using the fixed and random effect model, the Hausman test was used to guide the choice of the best model (Suleiman, Oyedokun & Adeolu, 2021).

Methodology

The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design as it attempts to study a subset of a population at a point in time and to investigate the effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors on the sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was adopted as the study instrument. The sample size was computed using the Raosoft online sample size calculator for a finite population. From the Raosoft calculator, 360 is considered appropriate for a population of 5,710 employees of six (6) registered Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria (Nestle Nigeria Plc., Procter & Gamble, PZ Cussons, Unilever Nigeria Plc., Cadbury, and Friesland Campina WAMCO Nigeria Plc). These FMCGs manufacturers account for 85% of the market share of the consumer goods industry in Nigeria. The geographical setting for the study was Lagos state given that 70% of the FMCG manufacturers in Nigeria have their head office in the State (Euromonitor International, 2022). To address the issue of anticipated non-response, 20% (72) of the sample size was added to the computed sample of 360. The addition of the 72 is to address issues of anticipated non-response from the respondents and this procedure is in concomitance with existing literature (Onamusi, 2021).

Table 1: Response Rate

Responses	Frequency	Percent
Completed usable copies of questionnaire	383	88.65%
Unusable, unreturned and disqualified questionnaires	49	11.34%
Total	432	100%

Source: Field Survey Results, 2022

Table 1 shows that a total of four hundred and thirty-two (432) copies of questionnaire were administered, and four hundred and six (406) copies were returned. 383 respondents' copies were certified as duly filled and considered usable. The useable questionnaire represented 88.65% response rate.

Results

To test the null hypotheses of this study, PLS-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) was used through the SmartPLS statistical platform version 4.0. The study used the PLS-algorithm's command which is appropriate for predicting effect-relationship, ran the bootstrapping to ascertain the level of significance of the prediction, and ran blindfolding to determine the predictive relevance of the structural model specified. Hence, the choice of PLS-SEM (via SmartPLS) is because it is a more advanced multivariate analytical technique which performs multiple regression, factor analysis, and provides a pictorial model of the interactions in a study with the push of one command as against running an isolated analysis using SPSS (Adeyemo, Adie & Onomusi, 2022). In addition, according to Asihkia, Adewole and Onamusi (2022) the SmartPLS statistical platform offers a more strict and robust analysis compared with the outcomes of SPSS.

H₀1: Corporate governance has no significant effect on the sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

The independent variable, corporate governance is measured by accountability, leadership, and stakeholder management while sustainability constitutes the dependent variable and measured by social (CSR), environmental and economic performance (Profitability). Data from three hundred and eighty-three (383) respondents were collated for the analysis. The result of the PLS-SEM is presented in three model (see figure 1, 2 & 3; table 2). Figure one shows the path analysis, figure two shows the t values which confirm the significance of the path analysis, and figure three shows Q^2 which confirms the

predictive relevance of the structural model (t value above 1.96 and Q^2 above zero confirm a statistically significant effect and that the structural model specified is relevance). Each model comprised of an outer model which shows the factor loadings (correlation) of each item in relation to the latent variable and the inner model termed the structural model (predictive model) which explains the interactions between the independent (corporate governance) variable(s) and the dependent (sustainability) variable in a study. Table 2 provides a tabular representation of the information in Figure 1, 2 & 3.

Figure 1 Path Analysis for Hypothesis One
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0

Figure 2 T-Statistics for Hypothesis One
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0

Figure 3: Q² Statistics for Hypothesis One
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS 4.0

Table 2: Summary of the PLS -SEM for the effect of Corporate Governance on Sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria

Path Description	Original		t	Sig.	f ²	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.
	sample (o)	Unstandardized Beta						
						0.729	0.710	0.000 0.391
Accountability → Sustainability	0.116		0.751	0.45	0.044			
Agile Leadership → Sustainability	0.533		3.148	0.002	0.529			
Stakeholder management → Sustainability	0.370		2.452	0.015	0.311			

Source: Researcher’s R result via SmartPLS Version 4.0, 2022

Table 2 presents the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the effect of corporate governance dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. The Adjusted R² was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results, the adjusted coefficient of determination (*Adj R²*) of 0.710 showed that corporate governance dimensions explained 71% of the variation in sustainability of FMCGs manufactures under study while the remaining 29% variation in sustainability is explained by other exogenous variables different from corporate governance dimensions considered in this study and the effect is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval and p value less than 0.05. This result suggests that corporate governance dimensions influence 71% of the sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The path coefficient of each corporate governance dimensions (accountability, leadership, and stakeholder management) represents the coefficient of determination (β) which shows the relative effect of each corporate governance dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria. PLS-SEM results in fig. 2 and 3 revealed that all corporate governance dimensions have positive and significant effect except for accountability with insignificant relative effect.

Specifically, the results revealed that at 95% confidence level, Agile Leadership ($\beta = 0.533, t = 3.148$), Stakeholder management ($\beta = 0.370, t = 2.452$) of the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria were statistically significant as their p-values were less than 0.05 and their t-values greater

than 1.96. However, the relative effect of accountability ($\beta = 0.116$, $t = 0.751$) has a t-value below the acceptable threshold of 1.96 to suggest that the relative effect is statistically insignificant. Based on the path coefficient, the regression model is restated as follows:

$$\text{SUS} = 0.00 + 0.533\text{AGL} + 0.370\text{SMG} \text{----- (i)}$$

SUS= Sustainability

AGL= Agile Leadership

SMG= Stakeholder Management

Further analysis indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in agile leadership holds a potential increase of 0.533 in sustainability for the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Similarly, the result shows that a unit change in stakeholder management will lead to a 0.370 increase in sustainability for the FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Overall, from the results, agile leadership has the highest relative effect on sustainability for the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria with a coefficient of 0.533 and t value of $t = 3.148$. In second place is stakeholder management with a coefficient of 0.370 and t value of $t = 2.452$.

The PLS-SEM offers the opportunity to detect the effect size of the predictor variables (corporate governance dimension) on the outcome variable (sustainability) using the F-Square (f^2) statistic. Scholars provided threshold for f^2 Values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, represents small, medium, and large effects respectively. Table 2 represents the effect-size of all corporate governance dimensions on sustainability of the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria. The effect-size of agile leadership and stakeholder management were 0.529 and 0.311 respectively. With reference to Cohen's f^2 criterion, it is safe to say that agile leadership have large effect size while and stakeholder management has above medium effect-size on sustainability of the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Further analysis was conducted to establish the predictive relevance of the model using Stone-Gleisser Q^2 value. Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2017) posited that Q^2 values of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 represents small, medium, and large predictive relevance. Furthermore, Q^2 above zero have been suggested to confirm that the structural model specified is relevance. According to Table 2, the Q^2 value of sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria is 0.391. Hence, corporate governance has large degree of predictive relevance with regards to sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria. And for this reason, the structural model specified is relevant and has sufficient predictive quality. On the strength of the PLS-SEM summarized results in table 2 ($Adj R^2 = 0.710$, $p = 0.000$, $Q^2 = 0.391$), this study can conclude that corporate governance significantly affects sustainability of FMCGs

manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria hence, the study rejects the null hypothesis one (H_01) which states that the effect of corporate governance dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria, will not be significant.

H₀₂: Firm-specific factors have no significant effect on the sustainability of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

The independent variable firm-specific factor are measured by firm size and operational efficiency while sustainability constitutes the dependent variable and measured by social, environmental and economic performance. Data from three hundred and eighty-three (383) respondents were collated for the analysis. The result of the PLS-SEM is presented in three models (see figure 4, 5, & 6 & table 3). Figure 4 shows the path analysis, figure 5 shows the t values which confirm the significance of the path analysis and figure 4.6 shows Q^2 which confirms the predictive relevance of the structural model (t value above 1.96 and Q^2 above zero confirm a statistically significant effect and that the structural model specified is relevance). Each model comprised of outer model which shows the factor loadings (correlation) of each item in relation to the latent variable and the inner model termed the structural model (predictive model) which explains the interactions between the independent (firm-specific factors) variable(s) and the dependent (sustainability) variable in a study. Table 3 provides a tabular representation of the information in Figures 4, 5, & 6.

Figure 4 Path Analysis for Hypothesis Two
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0

Figure 5 T-Statistics for Hypothesis Two
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0

Figure 6: Q² Statistics for Hypothesis Two
Source: Researcher's Computation via SmartPLS V4.0

Table 3: Summary of the PLS-SEM for the effect of Firm-specific Factors on Sustainability of FMCGs Manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria

Path Description	Original	T	Sig.	f ²	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.	Q ²
	sample (o) Unstandardized Beta							
					0.453	0.428	0.000	0.234
Firm Size → Sustainability	0.309	2.671	0.004	0.152				
Operational Efficiency → Sustainability	0.497	4.344	0.000	0.394				

Source: Researcher’s Result via SmartPLS Version 4.0, 2022

Table 3 presents the results of PLS-SEM analysis for the effect of firm-specific factors dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. The Adjusted R² was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results, the adjusted coefficient of determination (*Adj. R²*) of 0.428 showed that firm-specific factors dimensions explained 42.8% of the changes in sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers under study while the remaining 57.2% changes in sustainability is explained by other exogenous variable different from firm-specific factors dimensions considered in this study and the effect is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval and p value less than 0.05. This result suggests that firm-specific factors dimensions influence 42.8% of the sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The path coefficient of each firm-specific factors dimensions (firm size and operational efficiency) represents the coefficient of determination (β) which shows the relative effect of each firm-specific factors dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. PLS-SEM results in fig. 4, 5, & 6 revealed that all firm-specific factor dimensions have a positive and significant relative effect.

Specifically, the results revealed that at 95% confidence level, firm size ($\beta = 0.309$, $t = 2.671$), and operational efficiency ($\beta = 0.497$, $t = 4.344$) of the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria were statistically significant as their p-values were less than 0.05 and their t-values greater than 1.96. Based on the path coefficient, the regression model is restated as follows:

$$SUS = 0.00 + 0.309FS + 0.497OE \text{----- (ii)}$$

SUS= Sustainability

FS= Firm Size

OE= Operational Efficiency

Further analysis indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in firm size holds potential increase of 0.309 in sustainability for the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Similarly, the result shows that a unit change in operational efficiency will lead to a 0.497 increase in sustainability for the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Overall, from the results, operational efficiency has the highest relative effect on sustainability for the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria with a coefficient of 0.497 and t value of $t= 4.344$. In second place is firm size with a coefficient of 0.309 and t value of $t= 2.671$.

The PLS-SEM offers the opportunity to detect the effect size of the predictor variables (firm-specific factors dimension) on the outcome variable (sustainability) using the F-Square (f^2) statistic. Scholars provided threshold for f^2 Values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, represents small, medium, and large effects respectively (Adeyemo, Adie & Onomusi, 2022). Table 3 represents the effect-size of all firm-specific factors dimensions on sustainability of the FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. The effect-size of firm size and operational efficiency were 0.152 and 0.394 respectively. With reference to Cohen's f^2 criterion, it is safe to say that firm size has above medium effect size while and operational efficiency has large effect-size on sustainability of the FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Further analysis was conducted to establish the predictive relevance of the model using Stone-Gleisser Q^2 value. Scholars posit that Q^2 values of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 represents small, medium, and large predictive relevance. In addition, Q^2 above zero have been suggested to confirm that the structural model specified is relevance (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sar. According to Table 3, the Q^2 value of sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria is 0.234. Hence, firm-specific factors have above medium degree of predictive relevance with regards to sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria. And for this reason, the structural model specified is relevant and has sufficient predictive quality. On the strength of the PLS-SEM summarized results in table 3 ($Adj. R^2 = 0.428$, $p=0.000$, $Q^2 = 0.234$), this study can conclude that firm-specific factors significantly affect sustainability of FMCGs in Lagos State, Nigeria hence, the study rejects the null hypothesis two (H_02) which states that the effect of firm-specific factors dimensions on sustainability of FMCGs manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria, will not be significant.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of Corporate Governance on Sustainability

The results of multiple regression analysis for the effect of corporate governance measures (accountability, agile leadership, and stakeholder management) on sustainability dimensions (Social performance (CSR), Environmental performance, and Economic Performance (Profitability)) of selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria established that the combined effect of the measures of corporate governance used in this study exerts a positive and significant effect on the sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria. However, looking at the relative contribution of the individual measures of corporate governance, stakeholder management exerted a positive and significant effect, agile leadership also exerted a positive and significant effect, while accountability was found to exert no significant effect on the sustainability of the selected firms.

Conceptually, the adoption of appropriate corporate governance enhances the sustainable going concern of organisations. Furthermore, as stated by Setyahdi and Narsa (2020) corporate governance has been appraised to provide assurance to investors on the efficiency of the firm leadership in running the affairs of an organisation, enhancement of business prosperity (Zinkni, 2019), and the incline organisations towards sustainable practices (E-Vahdati, Zulkifli & Zakariya, 2018). In addition, the finding of this study corroborates the researcher's definition of corporate governance which considers the mannerism by which a firm is regulated in an effort to address or meet the interest of the firm and its stakeholders, to be pivotal to the sustainable performance of the firm. Similarly, as stated by Oyedokun (2019) corporate governance has been considered as the way organisations are directed and controlled, in alignment with the interest of various stakeholders.

Empirically, the positive and significant effect of corporate governance on sustainability found in this study has been supported by the findings of some studies. For instance, according to Utami, Cahyana, Nimran and Iqbal (2020) in a study conducted in Indonesia to investigate the transformation of firms as a determinant of corporate hospitality and how such interaction impacts corporate sustainability found that Corporate Governance (alongside increased strategic leadership, corporate culture, business infrastructure, and corporate alignment through corporate hospitality) ensures a greater level of Corporate Sustainability.

This study result is also corroborated by the submission of Maali, Rakia and Khaireddine (2021) in a study conducted in the United Kingdom to investigate how social responsibility mediates the relationship between corporate governance and sustainability performance in UK firms, which suggested that corporate governance exerts a positive effect on sustainability. In further support of these findings, is the result of an empirical review conducted based on the review of literature from America and Europe on the linkage between Corporate Governance and Sustainability, based on the Global Sustainability Index and sustainable goals for the United Nation's sustainability agenda 2030 which found that corporate governance practices and process do aid the sustainable performance of firms (Antwi-Adjei, Kong, Kwame & Antwi-Adjei, 2020). Furthermore, the result of a systematic review conducted to establish coherence between sustainability management and performance in Urban Corporate Economy also concluded that sound corporate governance promotes sustainability performance by Lazaroiu, Ionesu, Andronie and Dijmarescu (2020).

Looking at the individual contribution of the dimensions of corporate governance interrogated in this study (agile leadership, stakeholder management, and accountability) and their respective effect on the sustainability of the selected firms interrogated; of corroborative relevance to the positive and significant effect of agile leadership on the sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies investigated in this study, is the result of a research conducted to investigate the impact of leadership and management on the sustainable performance of sampled manufacturing firms registered on the Suruhanjaya Syarikat Malaysia directory located at Klang Valley in Malaysia which found that, leadership exerts a positive influence on green and lean practices, while green and lean practices were found to influence sustainability performance positively (Foo, Lee, Ooi, Tan & Sohail, 2021). Similarly, in another study conducted by Iqbal, Abid, Arshad and Ashfaq (2021) in Pakistan to investigate the moderating role of authoritative and laissez-faire leadership on thriving at work by obtaining data from head offices of major schools also established that, the style of leadership and consciousness does have an impact on thriving at work, therefore impacting the growth and sustainability of the organization. The finding of this study is further supported by the result of a study conducted in Thailand to investigate the influence of transformational leadership on corporate sustainability capabilities and sustainable supply chain management, which found that transformational leadership has a positive impact on developing organizational sustainability capabilities by Amin, Hakimah, Madjir and Noviantoro (2019). This result also corroborates the findings of a study conducted in Indonesia to examine the mediating role of knowledge management on

the sustainability performance of organizations, which concluded that transformational leadership exerts a positive impact on performance sustainability (Sapta, 2021).

In addition, the positive and significant effect of stakeholder management on sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers interrogated in this study aligns with the findings of a study conducted on “Eni” Company (the sixth-largest integrated energy company in the world with operations in 41 countries including the United States of America, the United Kingdom, Italy, Egypt, and Nigeria) to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of stakeholder engagement on sustainability culture which found that, engagement of stakeholders contribute to the transformation of corporate culture to achieve the three dimensions of sustainability (Salvioni & Almici, 2020). This study finding is further supported by the submission of Talbot, Raineri and Daou (2021) in Canada to investigate the contribution of awareness, external pressures, and stakeholder consultation to the implementation of sustainability management tools which found that stakeholder consultation plays a significant role in the implementation of sustainable management tools in firms.

Finally on the relative effect of the individual measures of cooperate governance adopted in this study; this study found that accountability has no significant effect on sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies interrogated. Conceptually, the meaning of accountability varies, depending on what is considered as the rendition of account in a particular situation which ultimately defines what accountability should be under the circumstance (Pesci, Costa & Andreus, 2020). To reflect this submission therefore, the researcher defines accountability as the acceptance of responsibility and rendition of stewardship to stakeholders. In line with this definition, this study interrogated issues bordering on Legal Compliance, Sanction on Unethical practice, Ethical Awareness, Reward for Professional conduct, Display of Professionalism, Information disclosure, and Adherence to accounting best practice. However, following the findings of this study, it will thus imply that the interrogated indicators of accountability adopted in this study, do not significantly affect sustainability of the interrogated firms. In other words, the acceptance of responsibility and rendition of stewardship to stakeholders (accountability) did not significantly contribute to the sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Effect of Firm-Specific Factors of Sustainability

The results of multiple regression analysis for the combined effect of firm-specific factors measures (firms-size and operational efficiency) adopted in this study on the sustainability of fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria showed that the firm-specific factors exert a positive and significant effect on sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. Furthermore, the measures of the firm-specific factors adopted in this study are seen to exert a positive and significant relative effect on sustainability.

Conceptually the ideal firm size is that size that promotes efficiency (Sindhuja, n.d.), and is considered a significant factor in the determination of a firm's profitability (Gaio & Henriques, 2018). Also, Banton (2021) stated that efficiency is key to achieving the highest level of performance using available resources to meet set goals. Thus, the adoption of an appropriate firm-specific factor strategy, therefore, can be seen to enhance firm sustainability. The findings of this study corroborate the researcher's definition of firm-specific factors and operational efficiency which considered firm-specific factors to be resources and capabilities of the organization identified to be of relevant impact in deciding a course of action; and proposed operational efficiency as deploying resources in a manner that minimizes resources consumed to achieve the same or better output level without compromising quality.

Empirically, there exists a dearth of literature that has attempted to study the effect of firm-specific factors on the sustainability of firms in Nigeria. Of close contextual relevance, however, is the study conducted to investigate firm-specific factors (measured by firm size and operational efficiency) and sustainability dimensions (social, environmental, and economic performances) of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study used secondary data obtained from the 10 years financial reports of the interrogated listed companies but could not establish the impact of the firm-specific factors on all dimensions of sustainability due to the inadequacy of data in the financial reports. Nevertheless, the result of the study showed that firm size (measured by total assets) and operational efficiency (measured by the ratio of operating expenses to Net sales) exerted a significant negative impact on the economic dimension (profitability), while firm size was found to exert a positive impact on CSR performance. The difference in the findings of the study could be traced to the methodology of the research and the inadequacy of the data collected to address the environmental dimension of sustainability to enable a full analysis of the impact of the treatment variables of sustainability (Suleiman, Oyedokun & Adeolu-Akande, 2021). Furthermore, Osazefua (2021) studies have shown that not all efficiency ratio is rewarded with profit.

Despite the above, the positive effect of firm size on sustainability found by this study has been supported by some studies. For instance, as posited by Balasubramanian, Shukla and Chanchaichujit (2020), larger firms have been found to perform better in the environmental dimension of sustainability in countries across America, Europe, Asia, and Africa. Firm size has also been established to play a significant role in financial performance of France-listed firms and also found by a study carried out in Indonesia to exert a positive impact on the financial performance of the 117 interrogated firms listed on the Indonesia stock exchange (Makris, Charalabakis & Stavroyianni, 2021; Ifada, Indriastuti, Ibrani & Setiawanta, 2021). These positive findings however disagree with the result of another study conducted in Indonesia which among other findings established that firm size has no significant effect on financial performance of the investigated non-financial companies listed on the Indonesian stock exchange using panel data for the period 2017 to 2020 (Jumadi & Sjarief, 2021).

From the theoretical standpoint, the significant and positive effect of firm-specific factors on sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies interrogated in this study further strengthens the provision of the Resource Based-View (RBV). The RBV which is an inside-out perspective theory holds that the combination of both tangible and intangible resources of a firm gives birth to other specialised resources referred to as capabilities that create strategic capabilities which provide a sustainable competitive advantage to organizations. This study's result is in concomitance with this theoretical perspective. Therefore, on the strength of the support found in conceptual, empirical, and theoretical submissions in extant literature with this present study's result, the study posits that firm-specific factors have a significant effect on the sustainability of selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturing companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The Joint Effect of Corporate Governance and Firm-Specific Factors on Sustainability

The result of the multiple regression analysis for the combined effect of corporate governance dimensions and firm-specific factors on the sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria, shows that corporate governance and firm-specific factor have a positive and significant joint effect.

Though, there exist a dearth of empirical works of literature that have attempted to investigate the combined effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors either by interrogating the measures used in this study or through other relevant dimensions. Yet, the findings of this study strengthened the narratives of the Resource-Based View perspective. In agreement, Korl, Mahoney, Siemsen and Tan (2016) emphasises that to

achieve a sustainable competitive advantage, organisations must combine resources to create unique capabilities.

This study's findings align with this theoretical perspective. Therefore, on the strength of the support found in conceptual, and theoretical submissions in extant literature with this present study's result, this study posits that corporate governance and firm-specific factors have a significant effect on the sustainability of selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study conclude that there was a statistically significant individual and joint effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors on sustainability of the selected firms. Hence, the study established that corporate governance and firm-specific factors have a positive and significant effect on the sustainability of the selected fast-moving consumer goods manufacturers in Lagos State, Nigeria.

The findings of this study shows that corporate governance strategies and firm-specific factors capabilities have significant effect on the overall sustainability of the manufacturing companies examined. By implication, these findings should enable the regulators of the fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry in Nigeria to put appropriate measures in place to enhance the overall performance of the FMCG manufacturers in competing favourably with their counterpart in other jurisdiction and offer product of similar quality.

The following are the study recommendations:

- i. Given the significant and positive joint effect of corporate governance and firm-specific factors on organisational sustainability, management should take appropriate measures to enhance performance measures such as accountability, agile leadership, stakeholder management, firm-size and operational efficiency.
- ii. The combined effect of firm-specific factors measures (firm size and operational efficiency) was found in this study to affect organisational sustainability positively and significantly, with both measures (firm size and operational efficiency) exerting relative significant effect. On the strength of this finding therefore, the firms are advised to have a good understanding of the contribution of both their tangible and intangible assets and how the combination of these resources affects the sustainability of their operations.
- iii. The appropriate configuration of firm-specific factors need to be understood and taken seriously to ensure constant monitoring and reconfiguration to curb waste and to attain the highest possible level of efficiency without comprising quality.

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